

RESEARCH ON THE TECHNIQUE OF SENTIMENT ANALYSIS WITH SARCASM DETECTION IN MULTILINGUAL DATA

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ABSTRACT

The majority of our time is now spent on social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, WhatsApp, Snapchat, and many more. They are filled with a variety of ideas and viewpoints expressed as user information gathered through browsing analytics. Now we're discussing those that are often utilized in Twitter debates. It has become one of the most important tools for researching various emotions utilising the same database and thought analysis algorithms since tweets allow users to express their ideas and feelings to others. There are three distinct categories of tweets: good, bad, and ugly. In statistics, good data is represented by positive data, bad data by negative data, and no data by neutral data. A method for determining user sentiment and categorising it as either positive, negative, or neutral is sentiment analysis. Data mining is a crucial technique for gathering facts and examining viewpoints on social media platforms. To categorise tweets as excellent, terrible, or neutral, combine data mining techniques with additional techniques including text mining, natural language processing, and artificial intelligence. This project's primary goal is to understand the motivations behind the tweets. For convenience of data analysis, the model converts information from various tweets that are accessible in English, Hindi, French, German, etc. into one language, English. The model also recognises sarcasm since there are so many sarcastic tweets in the file. A suggested methodology that enhances cascade outcomes in emotional evaluation using machine learning. For this, a range of machine learning techniques and their combinations have been used to evaluate the recommended model. and the results have demonstrated that it performs better as a standalone classifier.

Keywords: Tensorflow, Social Networking Sites, Sentiment Analysis, Sarcasm Analysis, NLP.

I. INTRODUCTION

Natural Language Processing (NLP) is one of the most well-liked categories of cognitive processing. Between spoken language and computer language, it acts as a translator. These methods may be used by machines to locate, analyse, and categorise information. Performing record searches and giving feedback are also helpful. Understanding the particulars of the topic is beneficial in addition to understanding the textbook or discipline. It functions with both conventional and unconventional data. Language patterns are created using colourful items like social situations, idiomatic terms, and store talks. There are a number of issues in the NLP discipline that need to be solved. The area of NLP that deals with environmental assessment is quite important. Sentiment analysis is the act of looking at the writing on the page and figuring out the channel that corresponds to the content. The difference between a form appeal and a remark could be useful. The calibre of textbooks must be improved through research. Numerous analyses can be done using emotional intelligence. These computations allow for the discovery and restoration of many emotional states. On actual coloured objects, like words or phrases from reports, the analysis method is put to the test. prompt pen input. It is sometimes referred to as "exploring ideas" when specific information and solutions are provided. Certain methods are used by emotional intelligence to process data and sentences. Positive or negative messages might be requested. When examining the theory of thought, commercial data, anaphoric recognition, profiling, identifying non-conformity, etc. Numerous significant issues could occur, including. Nowadays, the majority of individuals use vibrant social media platforms to express themselves. Many people have already started to voice their hatred. Critique is the term used to describe the main issue with research theory. Communication via criticism often takes a diversion. It's a tragic situation. Criticism may also refer to a feeling of unhappiness. It is in opposition to the definition. There are several methods to employ discrimination, including in-person interactions, public discourse, written materials, and more. In everyday conversation, disdain is expressed through body language and facial gestures. Disdain is the term used when the user's voice alters.

Using adjectives like talented, severe, exaggerated, signature, and more, one may illustrate how criticism differs from other kinds discussed in textbooks. The least amount of stars may be processed to reveal the picture of the stars. Satire may be found in a variety of entertaining games. It is employed to inform the audience of the hand's contents and the function of the pen. When it comes to punctuation, capital letters, emoji, and other symbols, problems are most frequently encountered. One of the most crucial functions of analytical thinking is regarded to be conducting critical research. Twitter is crucial for understanding what tweets are saying. Additionally, it is possible to use it to predict the outcomes of future elections [23]. Finding product reviews on various e-commerce websites is made easier by this. including Amazon, Flipkart, and others. Facebook, Instagram, Telegram, etc. Identification of comments on social networking sites is useful. The boot of an application may be chosen to analyse client data using consumer preferences and insights [12].

When a statement contains irony, think of the person who, when questioned about a riddle, should not solve the puzzle and dislikes others who don't think they can solve the problem. Then he said that I would lose my mind over the issue. So, don't ask me these questions, please. Imagine a man who is really confident in his ability to solve challenging difficulties on his own when the expression is humorous.

He wasn't prepared to respond when a question was posed. He also said that I was annoyed with the puzzle, thus you're asking about the puzzle that improves people. Ironically, this problem causes a discrepancy between expectations and actuality. When sentences are poor: Consider a person who can calmly respond to challenging queries. However, when I asked a question that made him think hard, the person asking it made me angry.

This implies that it will be quite tough for you to respond to these challenging inquiries.

II. READING REVIEW

Comments, Tweets, Comments, Comments from several individuals with various traits. Location, current affairs, various materials, age, gender, and other variables all have a role. [9]. There are two distinct categories of negative communication, according to researchers: speaking or speaking and negative speaking [4].

The voice tag (POS), which may be connected to words in a text, is a unique kind of application. Each of these characteristics may be used to help identify the characteristics that elicit criticism [7]. Behavioural and linguistic scientists have thoroughly investigated the accounts [2]. Using the views from the Serbian WordNet ontology, several antonyms were found. To talk about items unrelated to the observer's content and classify them into predetermined groupings that give ideas, acquisitions, occurrences, and secret information, people utilise antonyms, positive poles, sensory cues, ironic signals, and speech cues. [8] [10].

The prerequisites are listed in [1]. Language is sometimes divided into three categories: positive, negative, and neutral. The effectiveness of the words is also graded on a scale of 1 to 5, with 1 representing more-or-less excellent performance and 5 better or extremely poor performance [11], [25]. The character of the circumstance might also be influenced by emotions. Simply said, emotional words and symbols have the same body when they appear to be similar.

Approaches based on corpora and dictionaries can also be used to identify the picture.

Positive conjunctions are similar and are used to show that different roles are being played, whilst negative conjunctions are employed the same and take different forms. Conjunctions are used to link sentences. The network offers material from Wordnet [11]. Tweets on Twitter regarding videos that were simultaneously shot in several cities across many nations. They can be divided into three groups: Need-To-Know Tips, Good Questions, and Bad Questions.

To get rid of pointless stuff, use the UH filter. [12]. Having a good thought process is essential for creating humorous sentences. A strong and common feeling is mood. It is important to think about emotional polarity [13].

He also references academics who claim that symbols are crucial for teaching machine learning systems to categorise and produce emotional responses. The text is initially transformed into vectors by the 2vec technique, which are then concatenated by the k-word algorithm. In Table 2, [13], the symbols and their meanings are succinctly described. The model suffers from time and labour complexity as a result of the usage of map reduction [18].

Slang is a tool for expressing feelings. Put the text into subjective and objective categories. The definition of emotional slang uses simple sentences. The various weights specified in [20] are used to determine the polarity of the points. Eight kinds of emotions—joy, disgust, confidence, surprise, anger, hope, sorrow, and fear—were derived from Sentiment Analysis and Social Cognitive Engine Sentiment Lexicon (SÉANCE EmoLex) [6].

The hashtag token was created for GATE, a programme that supports several post formats. The creation of a new algorithm is ongoing. The tokens are created and then mapped to a GATE dictionary that has been converted from the Linux dictionary. For comparable goals, algorithms like the Viterbi algorithm are also utilised. Remove the label from the empty match and turn it into a symbol [24].

Numerous numbers can be used to illustrate an underestimation. For instance, getting up at five in the morning is a lot of fun. The aforementioned illustration will demonstrate why it is uncomfortable to awaken at 4 AM [27]. To create the model shown in Table 1, some researchers divided the modifications into eight categories, then ranked them in unimportant terms [3]. Through the use of symbols, there is a connection between the sentiment expressed in a tweet and the sentiment expressed by an emoji.

III. PROPOSED REQUIREMENTS

The outcomes show the suggested model beats other product types in terms when compared to the content of the f-measure and the actual values a number of machine learning approaches and their combinations.

IV. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The 4 modules are as follows:

A. Interpreting Sentences for Sarcasm

Data Collection:

Predictive model training is mostly dependent on data in order to avoid prediction and drug control failure. Writing is hence the initial phase of design. There are several techniques to get information for sentiment analysis, including gathering information from tweets, discussions, and comments. As a result, Twitter, which makes use of both its APIs and data analytics tools from Amazon, provided the data structure. Once your data has been visualised, analyse their behaviour to determine what you can do with it. A tweet on Twitter provides information about the tweet, the person who sent it, where they are located, what they were saying, and other details.

B. Pre-processing of Data

At this point, the user receives the rules, which are then utilised to decipher the rules into language markers.

Step 2 - The data is then rooted and lemmatized after this procedure. At this point, the document's current phrases are translated into the present tense, the words' underlying roots are identified, and similar terms are discovered using a dictionary.

Step 3 - At this point, the key job is to get rid of any pauses that are there but serve no purpose.

Figure 1: Sarcasm Assessment Process Flow Diagram.

C. Feature Extraction

The following phase is feature extraction once the preliminary data has been processed. The data that is currently accessible for the design may be used to define various features, and various methods should be used to extract these features from the data. In a sentence, sarcasm can be masked in a variety of ways. In some circumstances, a good option is followed by a terrible one, while in other instances, the statement's tiny likelihood of having a problem makes it challenging. Identify the sentence's exact meaning. When a sentence has neither positive nor negative information, there is a strong likelihood that it is sarcastic.

Table - 1 lists several caustic terms.

Class Number	Feature	Sample Text
Class 1	both pleasant and terrible things exist	It is dubbed delicate sweetness even though it is not at all sweet.
Class 2	Following a positive statement, a negative one, and vice versa.	Oranges are sweet and tasty. They're in a shipping box and rotting.
Class 3	The statement raises a conundrum.	I was debating whether to purchase the item due to its (good/expensive) pricing.
Class 4	Following a positive statement is a negative statement, and vice versa.	The goods wasn't nice, but the delivery was.
Class 5	In the scenario, a comparison between terrible and worse has relevance.	Although I wish I hadn't bought it, it's better than losing money again.
Class 6	Compared to a superior product.	More delectable oranges are sold nearby, as far as I know.
Class 7	It suggests that the review's target product has a negative connotation.	I would be happy with this product if it were a throwaway.
Class 8	There isn't a clear good or bad.	I can utilise it in that way.

D. Different guidelines and techniques are used to spot sarcastic language in given sentences.

Different learning methods such as Vader Algorithm, Naive Bayes Classifier, Gradient are used to test the model for higher accuracy Amplification Algorithm, Support Vector Machine etc. More formal methods are also used to get more accurate results for detecting sarcasm.

Identifying Polarity:

The polarity score of the provided phrases is calculated using a variety of NLPs in this stage, and the sentences are then categorised according to the polarity score to show if the sentence is sarcastic.

Legal Rules Regarding the Detection of Mocking:

There are legal procedures that play an important role in the detection of mockery. Some are semantic, syntactic, prosodic, pragmatic, etc.

Lexical:

The initial stage of sarcasm detection is lexical. Its job is to take the user's phrase and use it to create tags for nouns, pronouns, adjectives, verbs, subjects, objects, and other words. He then uses his dictionary to delete the foolish terms and fix the incorrect ones. It stores several attributes using the idea of n-grams [7].

Semantic Methods:

This is an additional rule-based technique for sarcasm detection in sentences. In this sense, the sentence's semantics—which make up its meaning—are used as the foundation. People's emotions, including how they feel, how they communicate, and how they feel about other people, may be easily identified using NLP. This technique is used in conjunction with several graph-based algorithms to identify the sentence's properties, such as whether it is sardonic. This allows us to gauge the degree of irony in phrase [10]. As a result, it is employed to provide an analysis of the phrase [25].

Syntactic Approach:

The rule-based approach to detecting sarcasm takes into account some rules that must be followed to control basic sentence structure and construction. There are four parts of speech that play an important role here, these are adjectives, nouns, verbs and adverbs. Then they think of two languages and with the help of the body they connect each symbol to 36 different letters and then connect each label to its own group. For example - qualitative adjectives, quantitative adjectives, singular nouns, special singular nouns, etc. Word-specifier pairs can be used to represent features to improve performance [7].

Effective method:

Under this criterion, text is deemed as private for the purposes of sarcasm detection. According to this method, the more punctuation marks that are employed in the phrase, the more probable it is that a surprise will occur [7]. The character set has been condensed to the bare minimal characters in order to prevent splitting.

Prosody Method:

This rule-based method of fake detection takes into account voice sound and rhythm when doing the task. [10] They show their technique for automatically detecting sarcasm in contextual, spectral, and prosodic signals in this varied group of academics.

Activity:

This law takes certain elements into account to define sarcasm in a sentence as a method of detecting sarcasm. Syntax rules for nouns are defined here to establish the identity of specific words.

Figure 2: Data loss and utilised epochs graph

As the number of epochs employed in the model rises, the chart above demonstrates how much data the model loses.

Figure 3: Line Graph Between Used Epochs and Accuracy

The aforementioned graph shows how the accuracy of the model changes as the number of epochs used in the model increases.

Table 2: Vector support algorithm efficiency matrix over model

	Precision Value	Recall Value	F1-score	Promote Value
Negative	0.9009	0.9396	0.9198	9179
Positive	0.8905	0.8263	0.8572	5463
Macro Average	0.8957	0.8829	0.8885	14641
Weighted Average	0.8970	0.8973	0.8965	14641

We constructed a model and applied the Support Vector technique, yielding an accuracy of 0.897268.

Table 3: Nave Bayes method performance matrix over model

	Precision Value	Recall Value	F1-score	Support Value
Negative	0.8215	0.9489	0.8806	1838
Positive	0.8835	0.6527	0.7508	1092
Macro Average	0.8525	0.8008	0.8157	2929
Weighted Average	0.8446	0.8386	0.8322	2929

On the developed model, we applied the Naive Bayes algorithm and obtained an accuracy of 0.838457.

V. CONCLUSION

Data and sentiment mining arrays, such as Twitter Sentiment Analysis and Affront Discovery, are the end product. Its objective is to examine the sentiment expressed in tweets and use machine learning to present and interpret that sentiment so that, in light of the results, we may use the model going forward. The procedure entails gathering information, pre-reading textbooks, cognitive abilities, linguistic abilities, modelling, and testing. These search phrases changed over time, and the model was 85–90% effective. It does not, however, differ from the data. Additionally, when employing slang and short words, it performs poorly. The bulk of class divides struggle as classes increase. Therefore, thought analysis has enormous potential for new ideas and projects in the future.

VI. REFERENCES

- [1] Mondher Bouazizi and Tomoaki Otsuki, "A Pattern-Based Approach to Twitter Sarcasm Detection", IEEE Access Vol. 4, 2016.5477- 5488.
- [2] Prof. Anandkumar D. Dave thiab Nikita P. Desai, "A Comprehensive Study of Classification Techniques for Mocking Detection in Text Data", Proc.International Conference on Electrical and Electronic Optimization Techniques, 2016, p. 1985-1991.
- [3] Satoshi Hiai thiab Kazutaka Shimada, "A Mocking Method Based on Evaluation of Expression Patterns", Proc International Conference on Advanced Applied Informatics, 2016, p. 31-36.
- [4] Filatova, Elena."Scything and Irony: Corpus Generation and Analysis Using Crowdsourcing." LREC. Xyoo 2012, p. 392-398.
- [5] Sanjana S, Skanda M Bhat, B S Harish.Proc. International Conference on Information Engineering and Applications, 2017, p. 1-5.
- [6] Pyae Phyo Thu and Then Nwe Aung. Proc.IEEE 6. Ntiaj Teb Sib Tham ntawm Consumer Electronics, 2017.
- [7] Mohd Suhairi Md Suhaimin, Mohd Hanafi Ahmad Hijazi, Rayner Alfred thiab Frans Coenen. "Natural Language Processing-Based Features for Teasing Detection: A Study Using Bilingual Social Media Texts", Proc. International Information Technology Conference, 2017, p. 70.
- [8] Miljana Mladenović, Cvetana Krstev, Jelena Mitrović, Ranka Stanković, "Classification of irony and satire using lexical sources", Proceedings of the 8th Balkan Informatics Conference.
- [9] Setra Genyang Wicana, Taha Yasin İbisoğlu and Uraz Yavanoğlu, "An Analysis of Mocking Detection from a Machine Learning Perspective", Proc. International Conference on Semantic Computing, 2017, p. 469-476.
- [10] Chapter Manohar thiab Pallavi Kulkarni, "Kev Txhim Kho Sarcasm Analysis Siv NLP thiab Corpus-Based Approaches", Proc. Uluslararası Akıllı Bilgi İşlem Kontrol Sistemleri Konferansı, 2017, s. 618-622.
- [11] Shuigui Huang, Wenwen Han, Xirong Que, thiab Wendong Wang, "Emoji-Based Sentiment Word Polarity Recognition", International Conference on Computational Intelligence and Security, 2017.i, 134-138.
- [12] U. R. Hodeghatta, "Assessing the Trust of Hollywood Films on Twitter", Proc. IEEE/ACM ASONAM, Aug.In 2013, p. 1401-1404.
- [13] Hao Wang, Jorge A. Castanon, "From emoji to social interaction perspective", Proc. International Big Data Conference, 2015, p.2404– 2408.
- [14] Michael Sejr Schlichtkrull, "Emotional Projection from Emoji on Twitter", Proc. International Conference on Cognitive Information Communication, 2015, p. 539-543.
- [15] prof. Payal Yadav and Dhatri Pandya, "SentiReview: Text and Emoji-Based Sentiment Analysis", International Conference on Innovative Mechanisms for Industry Applications, 2017, p. 467-472.
- [16] Archana. R and S. Chitrakala, "Exploring pinning processing in calculating tweet sentiment—a big data approach", Proc.2017 International Information Processing and Communication Technologies Conference, p. 106-110.
- [17] Santosh Kumar Bharti, Korra Sathya Babu, thiab Sanjay Kumar Jena, "Recognizing Parse-Based Satire Sensitivity in Twitter Data", Proc. International Conference on Developments in Social Network Analysis and Mining, 2015, p. 1373-1380.
- [18] Dmitry Davidov, Oren Tsur and Ari Rappoport, "Semi-moderated Recognition of Sarcastic Sentences on Twitter and Amazon", Proc. Fourteenth Educational Technology Conference, p. 107-116.
- [19] M. Boya, B.Faltings, C.-C. Musat and P. Pu, ``A :) Worth a Thousand Words: How People Connect Interest to Emojis and Text in Tweets”, Proc. int.Meeting. people. Computers, September 2013, p.345_350.
- [20] Manuel, K.V. Truth and P.S.R. Krishna, "Targeting Internet Slang for Emotion Mining", Proc. Second Vaagdevi International Meeting. don't notice.machine. Real World Issues, December 2010, p. 9_11.
- [21] B. Pang, L. Lillian, tiab V. Shivakumar, "Like it? Emotion Classification Using Machine Learning Techniques," Proc.ACL Conference Empirical Methods Ntuj Lang. Process, Vol. 10. July 2002, p. 79_86.

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- [22] Chapter Soler, F. Cuartero and M. Roblizo, "Twitter as a tool to predict election results", Proc. IEEE/ACM ASONAM, August 2012, p.1194_1200 a. D.
- [23] Maynard and M. A. Greenwood, "Who cares about sarcastic tweets? Exploring the effects of sarcasm on emotional evaluation," at Proc. IX International Conference. Lang. Source. Evaluation, May 2014, p. 4238_4243.
- [24] S. Homoceanu, M.Loser, C. Lo_ and W.-T. Balk said, "Will I like it? Enabling product tracking based on opinion citations," Proc.IEEE CEC, September 2011, p. 26_33.
- [25] Justin Martineau and Tim Finin, "Delta TFIDF: Best Site for Sentiment Analysis", Proc.AAAI International Blog and Social Media Conference, May.2009.
- [26] Lakshya Kumar, Arpan Somani, Pushpak Bhattacharyya "It's great to have 2 hours to write an article! ": Pinning Detection in Numerical Parts of Text, arXiv:1709.01950v1 [cs.CL] Sep 6, 2017.
- [27] S.V.Manikanthan and D.Sugandhi "Mimo multi-cell interference technique based on radio frequency interference" International Journal of Computer Science and Emerging Technologies Electronics (IJETCSE) ISSN: 0976-1353 Vol 7, Issue 1 - March 2014.